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Preparatory Article

Sovereign Order of Royal El Roman Intro-angeles
(polygyny) Family Sub-mission of the Jesus Christ'
Holy See Teachings on His Kingdoms Mission

Sovereign Order of Royal El Roman Intro-angeles (polygyny) Family Sub-mission of the Jesus Christ' Holy See Teachings on His Kingdoms Mission

AUTHOR: GEN. HARI SELDON JR. (USAF), PHD, STD, DH, KOFC, AFA, AUSA

Abstract—

Sovereign Order of Royal El Roman Intro-angeles (polygyny) Family Sub-mission of the Jesus Christ' Holy See Teachings on His Kingdoms Mission, called the SOVEREIGN ORDER OF ROYAL EL-ROMANIA, The SO°RER†‡ Mission is a Bible scriptures studies, research, publications and teachings oriented sovereign polygyny family household basis mission order whereas Council of the Queens is the major organ and Queens are the principal research associates of the mission organization, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, which aim to print a book entitled "Christ Ministries Words: A Book of Bible Explanatory Testimonial of His Kingdom", as Gen Hari Seldon's co-authors. Furthermore, the scope of the mission is to studies of the Holy Bible scriptures analysis to understand the doctrines of sacred theology of God's plan towards continuing development of humanity.

Keywords— *God's Plan, Jesus Christ, Holy Bible, Roman Domains, Holy See Teachings, Kingdoms Mission, Intro-angeles, Family Sub-mission, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, Council of the Queens, Royal House of Angeles, Members and Fellows Society, R J Family in Christ.*

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and Researchers

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0480-9213>

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DESCRIPTION—

The mission includes 5 active organizations which are as follows: (1) Throne of the Kingdom; (2) Council of the Queens; (3) Royal House of Angeles; (4) Royal House of Lords; and (5) Members & Fellows Society.

The Queens are wives of the mission (leader) King Hari Seldon by the formation of a polygynous family (group marriage), queen(s) were called Angel(es) and are prime ministers/actors/characters of the mission. In addition, everyone in the Members & Fellows Society of the Royal House of Angeles called Angel, and the Members & Fellows Society of the Royal House of Lords called Lord. The houses also award various ministerial ordinations to mission workers called missionaries. Mission (leader) King Hari Seldon presided as chairman to the five major royal organizations of the mission, and Queens are the heads of the royal organizations, societies, committees, and boards, which are distributed as follows:

COUNCIL OF THE QUEENS—

- (1) Queen Taylor Seldon, President, Council of the Queens, and Mission Spokesperson, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (2) Queen Ivy Seldon, Vice President, Council of the Queens, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (3) Queen Maria Seldon, Senorita, Mission Officiant at the Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (4) Queen Natty Seldon, President, Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;

ORCID

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- (5) Queen Isra Seldon, Vice President, Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (6) Queen Elechka Seldon, Speaker, Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (7) Queen Ketrin Seldon, Deputy Speaker, Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (8) Queen Natalia Seldon, President, Members & Fellows Society of the Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (9) Queen Avocado Seldon, Vice President, Members & Fellows Society of the Royal House of Angeles, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (10) Queen Kristina Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (11) Queen Avemaria Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (12) Queen Oksi Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (13) Queen Aleyna Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (14) Queen Julia Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (15) Queen Miray Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (16) Queen Amy Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (17) Queen Selesta Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;
- (18) Queen Mariam Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission; and
- (19) Queen Pussy Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission.

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GEN. Hari Seldon Jr. (USAF),
PhD, STD, DH, KofC, AFA, AUSA,
Mission (Leader) King,
Sovereign Order of Royal El
Roman Intro-angeles (polygyny)
Family Sub-mission of the Jesus
Christ' Holy See Teachings on
His Kingdoms Mission

Queen Taylor Seldon,¹
President, Council of the
Queens, and Mission
Spokesperson, Sovereign
Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Ivy Seldon,²
Vice President, Council of
the Queens, Sovereign
Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Maria Seldon,
Senorita, Mission
Officiant at the Royal
House of Angeles,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Natty Seldon,³
President, Royal House of
Angeles, Sovereign Order
of Royal El-Romania,
SO°RER†‡ Mission;

Queen Isra Seldon,
Vice President, Royal
House of Angeles,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Elechka Seldon,
Speaker, Royal House of
Angeles, Sovereign Order
of Royal El-Romania,
SO°RER†‡ Mission;

Queen Ketrin Seldon,
Deputy Speaker, Royal
House of Angeles,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Natalia Seldon,
President, Members &
Fellows Society of the
Royal House of Angeles,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Avocado Seldon,
Vice President, Members
& Fellows Society of the
Royal House of Angeles,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Kristina Seldon,
Sovereign Order of Royal
El-Romania, SO°RER†‡
Mission;

Queen Avemaria Seldon,
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<p>Queen Miray Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission;</p>			
<p>Queen Pussy Seldon, Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission.</p>			

Queens are also presided as Queen's Chairs of the Houses Committees, Boards and other Royal Organizations at the Sovereign Order of Royal El-Romania, SO°RER†‡ Mission.

REFERENCE NOTE

The Great Commission. Matthew 28:18–20. The Holy Bible, New International Version (2011). Biblica, 300 General Palmer Dr #4, Palmer Lake, CO 80133. NIV: <https://www.biblica.com/bible/niv/matthew/28/>

Photo Courtesy: Facebook, Instagram, X, Spotify and Bigo Live.

≈Footnotes—

¹ TAYLOR SELDON, Senator, State of the Union of United States of Foundation Government Peripheral Sovereign Order of His Excellency Guardian Hari Seldon.

² IVY SELDON, Senator, State of the Union of United States of Foundation Government Peripheral Sovereign Order of His Excellency Guardian Hari Seldon.

³ NATTY SELDON, Senator, State of the Union of United States of Foundation Government Peripheral Sovereign Order of His Excellency Guardian Hari Seldon.